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NLRP7 functions in the brain through neuropeptide and neurotransmitter regulation.

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NLRP7 functions in the brain encompassed regulation of the dopamine pathway through control of dopamine biosynthesis genes like *DRD4*. Neuropeptides, like genes of the *NPY* receptor family were controlled by NLRP7 as were physiologically active peptide hormones like *GIRP*.